

GENE NAME	GENE ID	^(5')FORWARD PRIMER^(3')	^(5')REVERSE PRIMER^(3')
<i>NoDGTT5</i>	CCMP1779_3915	ATGACGCCGCAAGCCGACATCACC AGCAAGACGA	CTCAATGGACAACGGGCGCGTCTCCC ACTCC
<i>NoDGTT5</i> <i>PRO</i>	CCMP1779_3915	CACCGATAGAAAGTTGATAGGCAA	CCTGAAGATAAAGGAGTTGC

Table S3. Primers used for amplification of sequences of listed genes without stop codon for cloning into pEarleyGate 101 vector. DGTT5 PRO refers to *NoDGTT5* sequence including its native promoter.